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3 **1 Inequality of temperature changes under net-zero and overshoot pathways**
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10 **Abstract**

11 As the world warms due to humanity's continuing greenhouse gas emissions, almost every
12 location across the planet is also warming significantly. Under net-zero or net-negative
13 emissions pathways it is expected that global warming will greatly slow and global cooling
14 may begin. However, relatively little is known about the pattern of post net-zero local
15 temperature changes under these declining forcings compared with the warming pattern of
16 today. Here, we explore the robustness of local temperature changes post net-zero using
17 multiple modelling frameworks. We find that a distinct pattern of Northern Hemisphere
18 cooling and Southern Hemisphere warming can be found across temporal scales and model
19 experiments when examining local changes relative to global mean changes. This
20 temperature change pattern coincides with less warming or greater cooling in wealthier
21 Northern Hemisphere regions of the world compared with poorer areas, and this is also
22 common across modelling frameworks. The inequality seen in the pattern of present-day
23 warming, where warming relative to background variability is higher in poorer tropical areas
24 than wealthier high-latitude locations, will not reverse under net-zero emissions pathways and
25 may take many decades to begin to reverse under net-negative emissions. Our study provides
26 more detail on expected local temperature changes in a post net-zero world and highlights the
27 value in considering multiple modelling experiments for such analysis.

28 **1. Introduction**

29 Humanity's greenhouse gas emissions are causing the world to warm rapidly (e.g. IPCC,
30 2021). Anthropogenic global warming is associated with significant and substantial warming
31 across most locations around the world, albeit to varying extents. The greatest warming is
32 found over the Arctic and there is faster warming over land than ocean areas. To understand
33 the detectability or perceptibility of observed warming, it is useful to examine local warming

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3 34 relative to background climate variability (such as a signal-to-noise ratio). The most
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5 35 detectable warming is found in lower latitude regions and over tropical oceans due to the low
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7 36 interannual variability in temperatures in these areas (e.g. Hawkins et al., 2020; Mahlstein et
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9 37 al., 2011). As most wealthier parts of the world are at mid-to-high latitudes, this means that
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11 38 wealthier people tend to live in places experiencing less perceptible local warming relative to
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13 39 poorer people who are more likely to live nearer the equator (Harrington et al., 2016; King et
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15 40 al., 2023; Mahlstein et al., 2011).

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20 41 As long as substantial greenhouse gas emissions continue, especially carbon dioxide, it is
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22 42 expected that the world will continue to warm. If net-zero carbon dioxide emissions can be
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24 43 achieved then global warming should approximately be halted beyond that point in time,
25
26 44 albeit with substantial model uncertainty in the sign and magnitude of this Zero Emissions
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28 45 Commitment, or ZEC (Borowiak et al., 2024; MacDougall et al., 2020; Palazzo Corner et al.,
29
30 46 2023). Model uncertainty in global mean temperature change under net-zero emissions can be
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32 47 traced back to model differences in the declining radiative forcing (associated with how fast
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34 48 atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations decline under net-zero emissions), the planetary
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36 49 heat uptake, and the effectiveness of the land carbon sink (Williams et al., 2025). If
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38 50 substantial net-negative emissions can be achieved (i.e. carbon uptake by humanity's actions
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40 51 exceeds anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions) then global cooling would be expected
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42 52 (Schleussner et al., 2024). This will become necessary to meet Paris Agreement goals should
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44 53 we overshoot the 1.5°C global warming level, which is becoming increasingly likely
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46 54 (Bevacqua et al., 2025; Cannon, 2025).

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52 55 Regional patterns of change under net-zero and net-negative emissions pathways are even
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54 56 less clear than global-mean changes. Previous analyses of multi-model experiments suggest
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56 57 there is substantial inter-model spread in local and regional temperature changes under
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58 58 idealised net-zero emissions pathways (Cassidy et al., 2023; MacDougall et al., 2022).

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3 59 However, despite that uncertainty, there is some model agreement in projected cooling of
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5 60 Northern Hemisphere land regions and warming (or less cooling) in the Southern Ocean. This
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7 61 is consistent with understanding of the inertia of the ocean and expectations of persistent
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9 62 warming, especially in areas of upwelling (Armour et al., 2016; Chamberlain et al., 2024;
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11 63 King et al., 2020; Manabe et al., 1991). Under 21st century moderate net-negative emissions
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13 64 scenarios, similar patterns of change are found, although most analyses compare pre- and
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15 65 post-overshoot climates at similar global mean temperatures rather than change from peak
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17 66 temperatures (Douglas et al., 2025; Pfliegerer et al., 2024; Roldán-Gómez, De Luca, et al.,
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19 67 2025; Roldán-Gómez, Ortega, et al., 2025). Limited research on mean and extreme
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21 68 temperature changes under net-zero emissions points to greater cooling experienced in areas
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23 69 with a higher Human Development Index (HDI), although the signal is not very clear and the
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25 70 model spread is large under weak climate forcings (Cassidy et al., 2023).

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27 71 To date, most studies on post net-zero climate changes have focussed on single modelling
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29 72 frameworks (either with multiple simulations from the same model or with a single
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31 73 experimental framework run by several modelling centres) and found mostly weak local
32
33 74 temperature changes. However, each framework has its disadvantages. There has also been a
34
35 75 lack of analysis on exposure and vulnerability to post net-zero changes. In this study, we use
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37 76 three modelling frameworks to examine robustness of post net-zero temperature changes
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39 77 across temporal scales and forcings. We also consider the experience of different populations
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41 78 across the world in local post net-zero temperature changes and examine for relationships
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43 79 with vulnerability.

50 51 52 53 80 **2. Data and Methods**

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56 81 In this study, we use two net-zero emissions modelling frameworks and one overshoot
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58 82 experiment to examine local annual-average temperature changes and their implications
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3 83 where people live. Each of these frameworks has distinct benefits and drawbacks (figure 1)
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5 84 so there is value in considering all of them and seeking to synthesise information across them.
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8 85 We use the Zero Emissions Commitment Model Intercomparison Project (ZECMIP; Jones et
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10 86 al., 2019) experiment which involves multiple Earth System Models (ESMs) running
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12 87 simulations under zero emissions (figure 1a). These zero emissions simulations are run
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14 88 following different cumulative carbon emissions levels and branching from the 1%CO₂
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16 89 simulations where atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations increase by 1% per year. The
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18 90 branching points are at 750, 1000 and 2000 PgC cumulative carbon emissions, but most
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20 91 participating models only ran the 1000 PgC case. These simulations have benefits: they are
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22 92 emissions-driven, so diverse carbon cycle responses can affect climate responses (Sanderson
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24 93 et al., 2024), and these experiments have been run with multiple ESMs (Table S1). However,
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26 94 the simulations are highly idealised with no anthropogenic aerosol or non-CO₂ greenhouse
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28 95 gas emissions, and most simulations are run for one or two centuries at most making it harder
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30 96 to distinguish the long-term influence of anthropogenic forcing from internal climate
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32 97 variability.

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38 98 We also use the set of 1000-year-long net-zero emissions simulations run with the Australian
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40 99 Community Climate and Earth System Simulator ESM (ACCESS-ESM-1.5; Ziehn et al.,
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42 100 2020). These simulations are described in detail by King et al., (2024). ACCESS-ESM-1.5
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44 101 was run under net-zero carbon dioxide emissions for 1000 years branching from the high
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46 102 emissions SSP5-8.5 experiment at 5-year intervals starting at 2030. In this study we used the
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48 103 2030, 2045 and 2060 simulations (figure 1b). These simulations may be used to analyse long-
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50 104 term changes under net-zero emissions and the consequence of delayed emissions cessation.
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52 105 However, this is a single model set of experiments and previous work has highlighted inter-
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54 106 model differences in global and regional post net-zero temperature changes (Cassidy et al.,
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3 107 2023; MacDougall et al., 2020, 2022; Williams et al., 2025). Also, this is a highly idealised
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5 108 framework with unrealistic immediate cessation from high emissions.
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8 109 We use a moderate overshoot scenario (SSP5-3.4) which forms part of the suite of 21st
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10 110 century scenarios (O'Neill et al., 2016) and their extensions (Meinshausen et al., 2020) in the
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12 111 sixth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison project (CMIP6; Eyring et al., 2016). This
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14 112 scenario follows a high emissions path until 2040 before greenhouse gas emissions are
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16 113 rapidly reduced and net-negative emissions achieved in the late 21st century. The extensions
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18 114 beyond 2100 involve continued net-negative emissions and then a return to net-zero
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20 115 emissions in the late 2100s (Meinshausen et al., 2020). These simulations are characterised
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22 116 by a peak in global average temperature in the mid-21st century followed by decline and
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24 117 stabilisation (figure 1c). SSP5-3.4 is a multi-model experiment although only 11 models ran
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26 118 the extensions through to 2300 used here (Table S2). These simulations are run with a
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28 119 theoretically plausible greenhouse gas concentration pathway up to 2100 before an idealised
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30 120 path is applied to the extensions. A downside to these simulations is that they are
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32 121 concentration-driven rather than emissions driven like ZECMIP and the ACCESS-ESM-1.5
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34 122 net-zero runs and thus do not capture uncertainties associated with carbon cycle feedbacks.
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124 **Figure 1. Different modelling frameworks may be used to study post net-zero climate**

125 **changes.** Each framework has its own benefits (summarised in blue) and cons (in red). a)

126 ZECMIP involves zero emissions simulations branching from 1%/year increasing CO₂

127 concentration simulations (grey). These are zero emissions runs following 750 (yellow), 1000

128 (orange) and 2000 (red) PgC cumulative emissions. b) ACCESS-ESM-1.5 1000-year-long

129 net-zero CO₂ emissions simulations branching from SSP5-8.5 at 2030 (yellow), 2045

130 (orange) and 2060 (red). c) SSP5-3.4 overshoot scenarios with multiple climate models that

131 branch from SSP5-8.5 at 2040. a-c) All timeseries show global surface air temperature

132 (GSAT) anomalies relative to pre-industrial levels (piControl for ZECMIP and 1850-1900 in

133 historical period for ACCESS-ESM-1.5 and SSP5-3.4). These are annual timeseries except

134 for b) where a 31-year rolling average is shown. In all plots, example timeseries are shown

135 based on the ACCESS-ESM-1.5 model. The black lines represent baselines used in this study

136 with thick yellow, orange and red showing the periods which are compared with respective

137 baselines.

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6 139 To examine post net-zero changes in these frameworks we establish a base period and select
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8 140 time windows post net-zero for calculating average temperature differences (figure 1). For
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10 141 ZECMIP, we follow the protocol used in other studies (C. D. Jones et al., 2019; MacDougall
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12 142 et al., 2020, 2022) and take a 20-year window in the 1%CO₂ simulation centred on the
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14 143 branching point as a baseline and 20-year windows centred 25, 50 and 90 years post
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16 144 emissions cessation to examine changes on multi-decadal timescales. For the ACCESS-ESM-
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18 145 1.5 1000-year-long simulations, we examine the long-term effects of emissions cessation by
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20 146 using 200-year windows in each simulation. We use a baseline after emissions cessation to
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22 147 limit effects of abrupt changes to non-CO₂ gases (King et al., 2024). For SSP5-3.4 we use
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24 148 2050-2080 as a baseline period close to the GSAT peak (noting there is some inter-model
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26 149 variation) and compare to the periods 2100-2120, 2150-2170, and 2200-2220 to examine
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28 150 changes at different stages under a net-negative emissions path.
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34 151 We analyse the detectability (or signal-to-noise ratio) of local post net-zero temperature
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36 152 changes by dividing the changes computed as described above with a noise term. The noise is
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38 153 defined as the standard deviation of the annual-average temperature computed from the entire
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40 154 length of each model's pre-industrial control simulation, following previous work (e.g. Frame
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42 155 et al., 2017).
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46 156 All model data are regridded to a common regular 2° grid. We compute temperature changes
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48 157 and signal-to-noise ratios for each model and, in the case of the ZECMIP and SSP5-3.4
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50 158 analysis, we compute multi-model median changes at each gridcell. We also compute the
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52 159 level of agreement in the sign of temperature changes at each location. Several models have
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54 160 multiple ensemble members available (Tables S1, S2), so individual temperature changes and
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56 161 signal-to-noise ratios are calculated in individual ensemble members before model median
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3 162 values are computed. These model-median values are then used to calculate multi-model
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5 163 median values and agreement in sign, so models with multiple ensemble members do not
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8 164 have an outsized influence. To further explore the robustness of temperature change patterns
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10 165 across these model experiments and different timeframes while accounting for different
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12 166 global average temperature changes, we calculate local changes relative to GSAT at each
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14 167 location and relative to the global mean land-only temperature (GMLT).

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17 168 We are also interested in exposure and vulnerability to post net-zero temperature changes. We
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19 169 use gridded population and gross domestic product (GDP) estimates for 2020 based on
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21 170 Purchasing Power Parity (Murakami et al., 2021; Murakami & Yamagata, 2019) to draw
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23 171 insights in exposure and vulnerability. We first coarsen the original 0.5° grid to 2° by simply
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25 172 summing population and GDP values in the constituent gridcells. We divide the GDP by the
26
27 173 population to obtain gridded GDP per capita estimates. These GDP per capita estimates are
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29 174 then ranked and the global population sorted into income deciles (figure S1). The distribution
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31 175 of local temperature changes experienced by the population within each income decile is
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33 176 compiled and plotted for each of the post net-zero temperature changes and signal-to-noise
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35 177 ratios that are examined.

31 178 **3. Results**

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34 179 In the ZECMIP 1000 PgC experiment multi-model median, there is a pattern of post net-zero
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36 180 cooling over Northern Hemisphere land and warming in the North Atlantic and parts of the
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38 181 Southern Ocean (figure 2), consistent with previous work (Cassidy et al., 2023; MacDougall
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40 182 et al., 2022). There are few areas of consistent sign of change across the model ensemble, but
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42 183 agreement tends to increase as time passes after emissions cessation. There is also a slight
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44 184 tendency for greater cooling to be experienced by people in wealthier areas of the world and
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46 185 this difference increases with time.

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4 186 There are three ESMs which, in addition to the 1000 PgC experiment, ran the 750 PgC and
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6 187 2000 PgC ZECMIP experiments too. These three models simulate a similar pattern of change
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8 188 in the 1000 PgC experiment to the larger ensemble of eight models, albeit with less of a
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10 189 cooling signal overall (figure S2). The change under net-zero emissions simulated after 750
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12 190 PgC cumulative carbon emissions is similar to that for 1000 PgC, although with slightly more
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14 191 cooling (figure S3). In contrast, there is more of a warming signal under net-zero emissions in
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16 192 the 2000 PgC cumulative emissions level simulations (figure S4). The warming is stronger
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18 193 for poorer regions of the world in the 2000 PgC simulations and this pattern is seen across all
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22 194 three timeframes considered.

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196 **Figure 2. Short-term net-zero emissions projections have low model agreement, but**
197 **wealthier locations are more likely to experience cooling than poorer locations.** Multi-
198 model median local temperature changes for 20-year periods centred on a) 25, c) 50 and e) 90
199 years after emissions cessation. Stippling indicates less than 80% model agreement in the

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3 200 sign of the change. Box and whisker plots of population exposure to multi-model median
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5 201 local temperature changes by income decile at b) 25, d) 50 and f) 90 years post emissions
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8 202 cessation.

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14 204 When the changes in the ZECMIP 1000 PgC simulations are shown relative to background
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16 205 climate variability (figure S5), the cooling in the tropics becomes clearer relative to the
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18 206 Northern Hemisphere land cooling seen in the temperature change plots (figure 2). This
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21 207 results in a reduced difference between the population-weighted changes by income decile.

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24 208 The long-term changes under net-zero emissions as simulated in the ACCESS-ESM-1.5
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26 209 simulations suggest slight warming would be expected despite falling atmospheric CO₂
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28 210 concentrations (King et al., 2024). There are large differences depending on when emissions
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30 211 cease with stronger warming in the Southern Hemisphere and cooling in the Northern
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33 212 Hemisphere when emissions cease in 2060 relative to 2030 (figure 3). This results in different
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35 213 relationships between vulnerability and temperature change between the simulations with
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37 214 delayed emissions cessation resulting in greater warming for populations in lower income
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39 215 regions and reduced warming/more cooling for people in the wealthiest areas. For example,
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42 216 the gap between the median temperature change experienced in the poorest and richest
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44 217 deciles is just 0.08°C in the 2030 simulation, whereas it is 0.27°C in the 2060 simulation.
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46 218 When framed in terms of signal-to-noise, the post net-zero changes in the ACCESS-ESM-1.5
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49 219 simulations are strongly skewed towards poorer locations experiencing more detectable post
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51 220 net-zero warming due to lower interannual variability in these areas (figure S6). This is
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53 221 especially the case for the simulation starting in 2060.
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223 **Figure 3. Larger income-related disparity in exposure to temperature changes post net-**
 224 **zero over longer timescales and if emissions cessation is delayed.** As Figure 2 but using
 225 the ACCESS-ESM-1.5 net-zero simulations branching from SSP5-8.5 at a), b) 2030, c), d)
 226 2045 and e), f) 2060 and comparing 800-999 years after emission cessation relative to 200-
 227 399 years after cessation. There is no stippling as this is a single-model analysis.

228

229 Under SSP5-3.4, cooling is projected almost everywhere following the period of peak GSAT
 230 in the mid-to-late 21st century (figure 4). The cooling is stronger and more consistent across
 231 models in the Northern Hemisphere, whereas in the Southern Ocean there are regions of
 232 anticipated warming, even after decades of net-negative and then net-zero emissions. Cooling
 233 over land is more consistent and across all income deciles, the vast majority of populated

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234 locations are projected to cool. For income deciles 2 and 3 there is slightly less cooling
 235 associated with weaker temperature changes in southeast Asia particularly.

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238 **Figure 4. Under overshoot, cooling will occur, but local cooling is projected to be greater**
 239 **in wealthier areas.** As Figure 2 but using SSP5-3.4 and for 20-year periods at a), b) 50 years,
 240 c), d) 100 years, and e), f) 150 years after the 2050-2080 baseline.

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242 When the temperature changes are presented relative to local background variability (figure
 243 5), the cooling signal in tropical areas becomes more apparent. This results in greater
 244 negative signal-to-noise ratios in lower income areas, especially after several decades of
 245 cooling have passed.

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247 **Figure 5. Relative to local variability, the strongest cooling is projected in the poorest**
 248 **areas, but only after decades of net-negative emissions.** As Figure 4 but for Signal to Noise
 249 ratios instead of temperature change.

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251 Across the three modelling frameworks, there are substantial differences in the experimental
 252 set up and forcing pathways. If we examine their similarity by subtracting the GSAT change,
 253 we find some consistency of relative land cooling and ocean warming (figure S7). However,
 254 the relative amount of cooling and warming varies strongly with greater relative Southern
 255 Ocean warming when time passes or when net-negative emissions are applied relative to the
 256 shorter period of net-zero emissions in ZECMIP. If instead the global mean land temperature
 257 is subtracted and only the land areas are examined, then a more consistent pattern is found
 258 dominated by relative warming in the Southern Hemisphere and cooling in the Northern

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3 259 Hemisphere (figure 6; S8). While relative Antarctic warming increases over time and under
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5 260 net-negative emissions, there is a broadly consistent signature of relative cooling, especially
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7 261 in the interior of land masses and in the Northern Hemisphere, while coastal areas and
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9 262 Southern Hemisphere locations are more likely to experience relative warming.

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264 **Figure 6. Across experimental frameworks there is broad agreement on pattern of**
265 **temperature changes.** Maps of multi-model median temperature changes relative to the
266 global land average in a)-c) ZECMIP for 20-year periods centred on a) 25 years, b) 50 years,
267 and c) 90 years post emissions cessation, d)-f) ACCESS-ESM-1.5 net-zero runs for d) 300-
268 450 years, e) 550-700 years, and f) 800-950 years post emissions cessation, g)-i) SSP5-3.4
269 overshoot runs for g) 2100-2120, h) 2150-2170, and i) 2200-2220 relative to 2050-2080.

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271 **4. Discussion and Conclusions**

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3 272 While signatories to the Paris Agreement are aiming to limit global warming to low levels
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5 273 and net-zero emissions is an essential step on that pathway, there is little analysis of post net-
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7 274 zero climate changes beyond global average temperatures. The sparse research on regional
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9 275 and local temperature changes has largely used single modelling frameworks and identified
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11 276 some robust changes but also low model agreement in many areas. Here, we use multiple
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13 277 frameworks, each with distinct benefits, and suggest that broader consistent signals may be
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15 278 found by examining changes relative to global-average land temperatures. There is also some
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17 279 signal for lower-income locations and peoples experiencing more warming/less cooling than
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19 280 wealthier locations and people post net-zero, and this is suggested across the three
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23 281 experimental frameworks that were analysed.

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26 282 By exploring temperature change and vulnerability (using GDP per capita estimates for 2020)
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28 283 we show that there are substantial differences between the net-zero and net-negative
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30 284 emissions pathways considered. Given the ZECMIP results it appears likely that under a net-
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32 285 zero pathway, short-term changes would be small in most places. The ZECMIP results would
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34 286 suggest that after a few decades greater cooling for wealthier regions may occur unless
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36 287 emissions cessation is delayed. The ACCESS-ESM-1.5 1000-year net-zero simulations point
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38 288 to post net-zero warming on multi-centennial timescales, albeit based on one model. Under
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40 289 net-negative emissions, cooling is expected, especially in wealthier locations.

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43 290 By framing changes in signal-to-noise rather than temperature magnitudes, different patterns
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45 291 emerge. If warming occurs post net-zero (which is more likely if emissions cessation is
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47 292 delayed), it is likely that poorer locations will suffer more detectable warming than wealthier
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49 293 areas, as is the case in the present-day warming climate (Harrington et al., 2016; Mahlstein et
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51 294 al., 2011). In contrast, if the world starts to cool substantially under net-zero or net-negative
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53 295 emissions then the poorest regions would see greater negative signal-to-noise ratios than
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55 296 wealthier places. This would undo some of the historical and projected changes, but the
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3 297 SSP5-3.4 results would suggest that this benefit may take many decades post net-zero to
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5 298 become apparent.
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8 299 There are several caveats to note with this work. Here, we analysed temperature changes
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10 300 under net-zero and net-negative emissions pathways, but there are many other relevant
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12 301 climate impact drivers that should be investigated too. Comprehensively analysing the
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14 302 uneven climate effects of these pathways requires an examination of many other climate
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16 303 impact drivers, particularly when it comes to assessing exposure and vulnerability (Ruane et
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18 304 al., 2022).
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23 305 We used 2020 GDP per capita estimates while considering future changes in a post net-zero
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25 306 climate. While this is useful for contextualising changes relative to current patterns of
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27 307 vulnerability, it would be expected that these patterns may change in future. GDP per capita
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29 308 projections are made for 21st century scenarios but have their own caveats and assumptions
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31 309 (Murakami et al., 2021; Wang & Sun, 2022). The aggregation of GDP and population data to
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33 310 2° gridcells will result in a large variety of people and incomes within a gridcell, but using
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35 311 global model outputs necessitates such a coarse approach. Also, other measures of
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37 312 vulnerability could be analysed, including HDI, but the overall spatial structure of
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39 313 vulnerability is unlikely to differ. We use the GDP per capita data to define income deciles
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41 314 and examine differences in exposure to temperature changes between these income deciles to
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43 315 discuss inequality. In this sense we are examining inequality only through experience of
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45 316 projected changes, but it can be examined in other ways too that might account for different
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47 317 opportunities and emissions related to historical fossil-fuelled development.
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53 318 Additionally, there are other net-zero and overshoot modelling frameworks in development or
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55 319 published that could be studied. The Carbon Dioxide Removal Model Intercomparison
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57 320 Project (Keller et al., 2018), Tipping Points Model Intercomparison Project (Colin Jones et
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3 321 al., 2025), flat10MIP (Sanderson et al., 2025), and other CMIP6 scenarios (O'Neill et al.,
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5 322 2016) all incorporate relevant simulations for analysis like that done in this study. We
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7 323 focussed on ZECMIP, the ACCESS-ESM-1.5 net-zero runs and SSP5-3.4 to incorporate a
8
9 324 range of idealised and plausible net-zero and overshoot frameworks with the required data
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11 325 published. The next phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP7) will
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13 326 include greater emphasis on overshoot pathways and these simulations will become available
14
15 327 in the next couple of years (Van Vuuren et al., 2026).

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17 328 Overall, we hope that this piece contributes to a growing understanding of global climate
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19 329 changes post net-zero and their implications for different areas and people around the world.
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21 330 There are still substantial uncertainties about how the climate will evolve under net-zero and
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23 331 overshoot pathways (King et al., 2025; Schleussner et al., 2024), but this study suggests the
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25 332 growing inequality in local warming seen in the present day climate will not reverse under
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27 333 net-zero pathways and may take over 50 years of sustained net-negative emissions to begin to
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29 334 decline. Our work here builds on other analyses showing the imperative of rapid emissions
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31 335 reductions and earlier attainment of net-zero and net-negative emissions.
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56 343 **Data availability statement**

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3 344 The model data used here are available on the Australian node of the Earth System Grid
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5 345 Federation. Gross domestic product (GDP) per capita estimates for 2020 were calculated
6
7 346 from GDP and total population estimates for 2020 downloaded from
8
9 347 <https://warp.da.ndl.go.jp/info:ndljp/pid/12232413/cger.nies.go.jp/gcp/population-and->
10
11 348 [gdp.html](https://warp.da.ndl.go.jp/info:ndljp/pid/12232413/cger.nies.go.jp/gcp/population-and-gdp.html). The code used for analysis and figure generation will be uploaded and published.
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15 349 **Conflict of interest**

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18 350 The authors declare no competing interests.
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21 351 **References**

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